

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH CULTURE OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN BY MEANS OF TELEVISION PROGRAMS

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Abstract. *This article assumes that children's television programs are educational tools, including for our youngest, which are suitable for the age characteristics of children, serve to expand their thinking, are full of vivid images, can inspire high ideals, great and bright works.*

Keywords: *direct-emotional communication, aesthetic, cognitive, social and speech development.*

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the study of some stages of speech development. It is known that each person improves his speech throughout his life, acquiring language resources. Each age stage brings something new to speech development.

The most important stage of speech acquisition corresponds to preschool age. Timely and properly organized direct-emotional communication of a preschool child with adults is of crucial importance in determining how the child will begin to understand the speech of adults, when he will begin to speak actively and at what rate his speech will develop in the future.

Education is a process of purposeful formation of personality. One of the most important goals of these teachers and students is the formation of a person who is useful to society.

TV programs intended for children are a means of education. The performances provided to our little ones should correspond to the age characteristics of children, serve to expand their thinking, be rich in vivid images, capable of inspiring high ideals, great and vivid works. The most important thing is that the topics are understandable, cute and interesting, and the hosts should conduct them in literary language.

The child's interaction with fiction in the organization of preschool education ensures the implementation of his aesthetic, cognitive, social and speech development capabilities. However, it is necessary to take into account the aesthetic features of the activity, the child's capabilities should not be limited to imitation. For this purpose, the teacher-educator should use the following methods.

Preschool educational organizations should pay attention to the artistic value of a literary work - the expressiveness of poems, the unexpected development of the plot in a story. In speech activity, it is aimed at creating an emotionally enriched performing environment for the child to perform a literary work or a work of his own creativity (retelling in a group, expressive reading individually, reading in a dialogic form with adults). However, a work of art can not only be told in words, but also its individual bright sides can be staged as a result of joint actions of children and teachers, interpreted musically, shown with actions, pictures, and constructive models.

In preschool educational organizations, the teacher shows various television programs in the afternoon in the spirit of traditional (about animals and wizards) folk tales, well known to children, and non-traditional (about children, natural phenomena, objects) fairy tales of modern times. Author's special programs for children teach children to compose stories about interesting events from their lives, creating an environment for them to weave their own fairy tales.

Using preschool children's ideas about the uniqueness of the structure and typical characters of literary works, the teacher should focus attention on the development of children's speech based on these elements. Also, television programs that develop children's mental thinking serve to form children's speech skills.

In addition, verbal games encourage children to create playful and funny situations based on rhyming games, word formation, continuation of poems and rhymes, as well as inventing comparisons. For example, coming up with new expressive names that reflect the characters of literary works, or new names for objects and events depicted in the work, helps the child increase his vocabulary along with logical thinking.

To develop aesthetic perception and creativity of television programs related to nature, it is effective to use thematic grouping of works. It teaches children the image depicted in different works and its development within one work; allows changing contexts when considering the same subject areas, demonstrating the interdependence of different forms of figurative expressions (words, movements, sounds, images).

The following forms are also possible: the teacher introduces children to a group of works and, based on them, directs the children's work to search for various figurative solutions to open universal cognitive problems (problems of the living and the dead, good and evil, beauty and ugliness). Obviously, during the search, the problems themselves are not formed in a generalized form, but only a joint discussion of various literary images and plots, as well as situations created by the children themselves, takes place.

Dialogic speech should be the leading tool of pedagogical work. The teacher should create conditions for children to participate in establishing communication, effectively using dialogic speech, and solving problem situations. Children, complementing each other, describe the content of the stories together, introduce into the discussion process elements of interpretation and evaluation of the events described, literary characters and their actions. In the process of dialogical discussion, the teacher should introduce elements of problematization of the artistic content, i.e. various interpretations, ask open questions and reason about them (for example, what remains of the fairy tale after it is told?).

The teacher evaluates the effectiveness of his work not only by how children behave in class, but also observes their behavior in free activities: notes the plots of games and pictures on literary themes, the content of children's thoughts, their independent word; encourages children to act with books - individually or together to look at and read. The teacher answers children's questions and individually talks with them about the content of the works they like.

Along with collecting the most interesting thoughts of children, stories about their personal experience, poems and fairy tales invented by children, the teacher needs to form children's attitude to books. On the basis of these materials it is necessary to organize the creation of a "book" by the children themselves. These can be fairy tales woven by children, stories about personal impressions, songs, a collection of poems decorated with children's drawings, a handwritten journal and skills.

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